

MODERNIZATION OF EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE, HEAT SUPPLY SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *The article describes in detail the advantages of using heat pumps, such as increased energy efficiency, saving heating costs, and reducing emissions into the atmosphere. The principles of operation and application of electric discharge technologies for water treatment, ensuring its safety and purity, are also considered.*

Various schemes for integrating new technological solutions into existing heat supply systems are proposed in order to increase efficiency and reduce costs. Examples of successful implementation of these solutions in various cities and regions are given.

The study shows that the modernization of heat supply systems using modern technologies can significantly improve the quality of customer service, reduce the burden on natural resources and make heating more environmentally friendly.

Keywords: *efficiency, heat supply, heat pump, heat supply systems, diaphragm discharge, disinfection.*

Аннотация: *В статье подробно изложены преимущества использования тепловых насосов, таких как повышенная энергоэффективность, экономия затрат на отопление, сокращение выбросов в атмосферу. Также рассмотрены принципы работы и применение электроразрядных технологий для обработки воды, обеспечивающих ее безопасность и чистоту.*

Предложены различные схемы интеграции новых технологических решений в существующие системы теплоснабжения с целью повышения эффективности и снижения затрат. Даны примеры успешной реализации данных решений в различных городах и регионах.

Исследование показывает, что модернизация систем теплоснабжения с использованием современных технологий может значительно улучшить качество обслуживания потребителей, снизить нагрузку на природные ресурсы и сделать отопление более экологически безопасным.

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, теплоснабжение, тепловой насос, системы теплоснабжения, диафрагменный разряд, обеззараживание.*

Introduction

Currently, the development of thermal energy, in the context of the desire to create energy-efficient and safe heat supply systems in Tajikistan, the task of developing low-cost ways to modernize existing systems is becoming urgent.

One of the important directions of such modernization may be the use of innovative technologies, such as heat pumps, which allow efficient use of renewable energy sources. Also, the introduction of electric discharge technologies for water treatment can help improve the quality of water supply and reduce the load on heat supply systems.

For successful modernization of heat supply systems, it is also important to pay attention to assessing the current state of the systems, identifying bottlenecks and

problem areas in order to determine the most optimal and effective ways to improve them.

The main problems of the existing infrastructure and heat supply systems:

The development and implementation of low-cost ways to modernize heat supply systems in Tajikistan will help reduce energy consumption, increase their efficiency, improve the quality of life of the population and contribute to the achievement of the country's sustainable development goals. It is important to continue working on the development and improvement of thermal power engineering, taking into account modern technological advances.

In addition to such methods, the use of renewable energy sources (RES) is one of the key ways to compensate for part of the consumed energy resources. In Tajikistan, with its abundance of solar and hydropower, the introduction of solar and hydroelectric power plants can significantly reduce the consumption of traditional energy resources and make the heat supply system more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

Redistribution of excess energy in existing systems is also an effective way to optimize energy consumption and increase the efficiency of heat supply systems.

The use of electric discharge technologies for water disinfection during open water collection of mains water for hot water supply (DHW) is another important approach. This technology makes it possible to disinfect water without the use of chemicals, which makes the process more environmentally friendly.

All these methods can be successfully implemented into Tajikistan's heat supply system to improve its efficiency, environmental sustainability and reduce dependence on traditional energy resources. The continuation of work on the modernization of heat supply systems using innovative technologies and approaches will allow the country to move towards sustainable and energy efficient development.

Modernization methods and their advantages:

Advantages, heat supply systems using renewable energy sources (RES) have a number of advantages compared to traditional systems:

1. Reducing energy costs: Renewable energy sources provide energy sources that are infinitely replenished and not exhausted, such as solar and wind energy. The use of these sources makes it possible to reduce or even completely eliminate the consumption of traditional energy resources such as gas or coal.

2. Environmental cleanliness: Renewable energy sources are environmentally friendly and do not produce harmful emissions into the atmosphere. The use of renewable energy contributes to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing environmental impact.

3. Increasing the autonomy of systems: Heat supply systems based on renewable energy sources can be more autonomous and less dependent on centralized energy

systems. This increases the resistance of heat supply systems to possible failures and external influences.

The use of renewable energy in heat supply systems reduces energy consumption, contributes to the preservation of the environment and contributes to the creation of more independent and sustainable systems. Such systems are an important step towards energy efficiency, environmental sustainability and improving the quality of life of society.

In modern conditions of renewable energy use, schemes using low-potential ambient heat using heat pump installations (TNUS) have reliably secured their place [4-8].

In modern conditions, the use of low-potential environmental heat with the help of heat pump installations (TNUS) is becoming increasingly popular and in demand in modern conditions. Heat pumps are used to transfer heat from low-potential sources (e.g. soil, air, water) to a heating or water supply system, providing efficient and environmentally friendly heating of buildings.

The advantages of using heat pump installations include:

1. Energy efficiency: Heat pumps can provide more efficient use of energy, as they do not produce heat, but simply transfer it from one place to another. This allows you to reduce energy consumption and reduce the cost of heating buildings.

2. Ecological cleanliness: Heat pumps operate on the basis of renewable energy sources, such as low-potential environmental heat, which makes them environmentally friendly and helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

3. Independence from traditional energy resources: The use of heat pumps reduces dependence on traditional energy resources such as gas or coal, and ensures reliable and stable heating of buildings.

Thus, the use of circuits with heat pump installations makes it possible to effectively use low-potential environmental heat to provide heating for buildings, reducing energy costs, improving the environmental situation and increasing independence from traditional energy sources.

However, despite the various technologies for collecting environmental heat, all the technological solutions offered today using TNU have one drawback that limits their scope of application. This disadvantage is significant investments in the implementation of TNCs in existing heating systems, especially in conditions of dense urban development, when it becomes difficult to create wells or receiving tanks to organize access to low-potential thermal energy.

The solution to the cost problem may be the transition to a new heat source, access to which does not require significant reconstruction of the original heat supply scheme.

When analyzing heating systems, even if it is not used to heat rooms during the non-heating period, it may still contain heat that can be used as a low-potential heat source for other purposes, such as providing hot water or maintaining a warm indoor microclimate.

Based on this conclusion, a method of hot water supply was developed, which is based on the use of heating systems as a source of low-potential energy in the non-heating period, represents a significant improvement over traditional analogues.

The advantages of this method include:

1. Relatively low capital costs: Using existing heating systems as a heat source allows you to reduce the capital costs of creating new hot water heating systems. This makes the developed method more cost-effective and accessible to a wide range of consumers.

2. Complete elimination of heat losses: The developed method eliminates heat losses from subscriber input pipelines, which helps to reduce energy consumption and increase the efficiency of the system.

3. Independence from a centralized heat source: The ability to use your own heating systems as a heat source makes facilities more autonomous and independent of centralized resources. This increases the flexibility and reliability of the system.

Utilization of excess heat of the building: The developed method allows the utilization of excess heat of the building during the non-heating period, which contributes to the optimal use of energy resources and increased energy efficiency.

At the same time, the developed method of hot water supply is an innovative and promising solution that combines energy efficiency, efficiency and sustainability, meeting modern requirements for reducing resource consumption and environmental protection.

For example, heat in a central heating system or in underfloor heating can be used to maintain the temperature of hot water in a boiler or to heat air in a ventilation system. This makes it possible to effectively use the existing heat and reduce the energy consumption of the building as a whole.

Thus, the use of heating systems as a source of low-potential heat in the non-heating period opens up new opportunities for energy efficient and sustainable use of resources, helping to reduce energy costs and reduce environmental impact.

Examples of successful modernization projects:

To achieve the claimed result, the water going to the hot water supply is heated to the required temperature in the condenser of the heat pump installation due to the heat received from a low-potential source in the evaporator of the heat pump installation, and supplied to consumers, and mains water circulating in a closed circuit of the building heating system is used as a low-potential heat source in the

evaporator[5-9].

Fig. 1 – building hot water supply system: 1 – supply pipeline, 2 – return pipeline, 3 – valves, 4 – water meter, 5 – mud pump, 6 – pressure gauge, 7- thermometer, 8 - elevator, 9 – heating device.

The method of hot water supply is implemented as follows:

During the non-heating period, when the heating and hot water supply system of the building is switched to the hot water supply mode, the switch to a closed circulation circuit inside the heating system of the building takes place. Let's look at how this happens: A closed circulation circuit is created by closing the shut-off valve 8, which separates the building's heating system from external heating networks. Simultaneously with the closure of the valve 8, the valve 9 opens, which allows the coolant to circulate inside the closed circuit of the heating system. The circulation pump 10 drives the coolant inside the closed circuit of the heating system. This allows the heat to be evenly distributed throughout the system and ensure the supply of hot water to the desired points of consumption.

After passing through the heating devices 11, in which the coolant takes excess heat from the premises, it is sent to the evaporator of the heat pump unit 5. In the evaporator, the coolant is cooled by transferring the collected heat to the refrigerant, which circulates in the circuit of the heat pump unit.

The evaporator in the heat pump installation plays a role in the process of the heat pump operation cycle. Here, the refrigerant evaporates due to the heat received from the coolant. As a result, the refrigerant turns into a gaseous state and becomes a hot gas. This hot refrigerant gas then enters the compressor of the heat pump unit, which increases the pressure and temperature of the gas. After that, the hot gas goes to the condenser, where it gives off the accumulated heat to the heating system or hot

water supply, and goes back to the liquid state. During the operation of the heat pump unit, the heat that the refrigerant received in the evaporator is given off in the condenser of the heat pump unit. In this case, water going to the hot water supply (DHW) is used as the heated medium for the condenser. The water supplied to the DHW 3 passes through the condenser of the heat pump unit 4, where it is heated by heat transfer from the refrigerant. The heat generated during the condensation of the refrigerant is transferred to the water inside the pipe, increasing its temperature. As a result, the water is heated to a temperature of at least 60 °C, which meets the safety standards for hot water supply. After heating in the condenser, hot water is supplied to the consumer for use. Thus, the heat generated during the operation of the heat pump unit is effectively used to provide hot water supply to the building, which saves energy and increases consumer comfort.

When the valve 8, valve 7 and the three-way valve 12 are simultaneously closed, the circulation of the coolant in the supply and return pipelines of the subscriber input of the building stops. This makes it possible to completely eliminate heat losses from these pipelines, since the coolant stops circulating and loses heat.

When the valve 7 is closed, the DHW heat exchanger 6 does not participate in the heat exchange process. The DHW heat exchanger is designed to transfer heat from the refrigerant from the heat pump unit to the consumed water, heating it to the required temperature. When the valve 7 is closed, the circulation of the coolant and, accordingly, heat stops, which means that the DHW heat exchanger will not function.

At the same time, the closure of the corresponding valves and valves allows you to effectively manage heat losses and regulate heat transfer processes in the heating and hot water supply system of the building in accordance with current needs.

Yes, the use of water circulating in the building's heating system during the non-heating period, as a low-potential source of heat, allows the building to be provided with hot water regardless of the centralized heat source. This method makes it possible to effectively use a DHW heat exchanger to heat water to the required temperature, using the already available thermal energy, which is usually lost during the heating process.

At the same time, it is necessary to have an effective process control and regulation system in order to ensure a stable and reliable hot water supply to the building. This approach also has the advantage of relatively low capital costs, since its implementation does not require the construction of additional heating systems or the installation of expensive equipment.

Thus, the use of water circulating in the heating system as a source of heat for hot water supply allows you to save resources and reduce dependence on centralized heat sources, while ensuring comfortable use of hot water in the building.

At the same time, the economic effect is achieved through savings in switching to an autonomous heat source, savings from the absence of heat losses from subscriber input pipelines, as well as savings by reducing the cost of air conditioning.

The technology of heat transfer using TNU, in addition to local application for specific consumers, can also be used to solve the problems of redistribution of excess thermal energy in urban heat supply networks, which are characterized by the problem of abnormal heat release[4-10].

An analysis of the consumption of thermal energy by consumers equipped with heat metering devices in the city of Dushanbe showed a significant deviation of the real heat consumption from the calculated values.

The deviation of the actual consumption of thermal energy from the calculated values can have various reasons and have a negative impact on the operation of the heat supply system.

Some of the possible causes of deviations may be as follows:

1. Inconsistency of the technical condition of the equipment and metering devices. Damaged or faulty metering devices can lead to inaccurate accounting of thermal energy consumption.

2. Violation of the rules of operation of the heat supply system. Improper operation or disruption of technological processes can lead to non-standard consumption of thermal energy.

3. Inefficient management and control of the heat supply system. The absence or imperfection of a heat supply monitoring and management system can lead to inaccurate accounting and consumption management.

4. Illegal consumption or leakage of thermal energy. Illegal connection to the heat supply system or leakage of thermal energy can lead to a significant deviation in consumption from the calculated values.

To solve the problem of a significant deviation of the actual consumption of thermal energy from the calculated values, it is necessary to conduct a thorough analysis of the causes and take measures to improve the control and management of the heat supply system, as well as update and maintain equipment and metering devices. Monitoring and auditing of the heat supply system will help identify problem areas and take the necessary measures to optimize the operation of the system.

Maintaining comfortable temperature conditions in consumer premises is one of the main tasks for heat supply systems. A comfortable indoor temperature has a direct impact on the well-being and health of people, therefore ensuring optimal temperature is critically important.

With a general shortage of thermal energy, heat supply systems may face the problem of insufficient heat flow to ensure proper heating conditions. In such cases,

the introduction of modern technologies may be necessary for effective management and optimization of the system.

Modern technologies in the field of heat supply can include automated monitoring and control systems that optimize the distribution and consumption of thermal energy. Modern technologies may also include the use of energy-efficient equipment and heating systems such as heat pumps, infrared heaters and smart thermostats.

The introduction of modern technologies will help not only to ensure comfortable indoor heating conditions, but also to increase the efficiency of the heat supply system, reduce heat consumption and improve process management. Therefore, investments in modern technologies in the field of heat supply may be justified in order to ensure proper heat supply conditions in conditions of general under-supply of thermal energy.[4]

Calculating the efficiency of optimizing the heat supply from the CHP to the consumer, taking into account changes in the DHW load and outdoor air temperature during the day, is an important step to optimize the operation of the heat supply system. Modeling the system taking into account its real state allows us to take into account the parameters that can affect the efficiency of heat transfer from the CHP to consumers.

Reducing the temperature of the return mains water is one of the methods of optimizing the operation of the heat supply system. When the temperature of the return water decreases, the consumption of thermal energy necessary to maintain the set room temperatures decreases. This allows you to reduce the cost of heat supply and increase the efficiency of the system.

The economic effect of optimizing heat release can be manifested in reducing fuel or electricity costs, improving system reliability, reducing equipment wear and reducing environmental stress. In addition, optimizing the operation of the heat supply system can contribute to a more stable and predictable operation of the system as a whole.

In general, the use of methods to optimize heat release and reduce the temperature of the return mains water can bring significant economic benefits and improve the efficiency of the heat supply system, providing comfortable heating conditions for consumers.

Yes, indeed, the economic effect of reducing the temperature of the return network water and optimizing the heat release from the CHP is not marginal due to the limitations associated with different characteristics of heating networks and the needs of different areas for thermal energy.

There may be different thermal insulation conditions in different sections of heating networks, which affects the rate of temperature change in the system. Also, the

rate of temperature change of direct mains water at the CHP is limited by regulations and should not exceed a certain value in order to avoid a negative impact on the equipment and operation of the system.

In addition, heat consumption areas have different heat energy needs depending on the time of day, season and other factors. It also requires varying the temperature of the direct mains water to ensure optimal conditions for consumers.

Thus, although optimizing heat release and reducing the temperature of the return mains water can have an economic effect, this effect is limited by various factors related to the characteristics of heating networks and consumer needs. To achieve the maximum potential economic effect, it is necessary to take into account all these limitations and find the optimal solution for the specific conditions and requirements of the heat supply system[1 - 5].

Yes, the use of installations for the redistribution of heat flows along different inertial branches of heating networks can allow you to remove some restrictions and improve the efficiency of the heat supply system.

These installations allow you to change the temperature of the coolant in various directions, depending on the optimal daily schedule and the needs of specific consumers. This allows for more precise regulation of temperature conditions in different sections of heating networks and provides optimal conditions for consumers.

This approach allows us to take into account the various characteristics of heating networks, the needs of specific consumers and the characteristics of the load in different time periods. This helps to optimize the heat release from the CHP and reduce the cost of heat supply.

The use of heat transfer units can become an effective tool for improving the operation of the heat supply system, increasing its efficiency and reducing operating costs. At the same time, it is important to carefully design and configure the system to achieve optimal results.

Heat pump technology can be an effective way to redistribute heat flows in a heat supply system. The idea is that a heat pump can be used to maintain an optimal coolant temperature in various sections of heating networks.

Figure 2 shows the operation scheme of a heat pump for heat redistribution. During periods of increased heat load, the most remote sections of heating networks can be heated using a heat pump, which effectively transfers heat from the environment to the system.

During periods of reduced heat load, the heat pump can be used to increase the temperature in the near sections of heating networks, providing optimal conditions for consumers.

Fig. 2. – Diagram of the heat supply complex.

**1 – heat supply source; 2,3 – heat pump condenser; 4,5 – heat pump evaporator;
6 – heat pump; 7 – drive; 8 – consumer; 9 – second consumer; 10,11,12,13 – flow regulators;
14 – pipelines of direct mains water; 15 – pipelines of reverse mains water.**

This method of heat redistribution makes it possible to more effectively manage temperature conditions in the heat supply system, optimize the operation of the system and reduce energy costs.

However, when using heat pump technology, it is necessary to take into account the design, installation and maintenance of these devices in order to achieve maximum efficiency and economic benefits.

Heat pump technology can really be a good addition to an existing district heating system. The use of heat pumps makes it possible to efficiently redistribute heat in the network, providing optimal temperature conditions for consumers.

The greater the difference between the cost of thermal energy produced using heat pumps and the cost of thermal energy produced by traditional methods, the faster the project to implement this technology can pay off. Ultimately, the lower cost of heat production using heat pumps can lead to cost savings over a long distance.

However, it is important to take into account all aspects of the design, installation and operation of the heat pump system in order to ensure optimal operation and payback of the project. It is also necessary to conduct a thorough analysis of the energy market, tariffs, consumer needs and other factors in order to make informed decisions on the implementation of this technology.

The use of electric discharge technologies in an electric heating system can really increase the efficiency of the heating process, as well as ensure the disinfection of water during open water intake from the cold water supply network for hot water supply (DHW).

Electrical discharge technologies such as corona arresters or ultrasonic discharge generators can be used to create electrical discharges in water. This leads to the formation of ozone and other reactive oxygen species, which have strong disinfecting

properties. Thus, in addition to heating the water, these installations can effectively destroy microorganisms and bacteria, which helps to improve water quality and prevent the spread of infections[4-7].

This dual use of electric discharge technologies provides not only efficient water heating, but also additional hygienic benefits. This makes it possible to reduce the cost of chemical treatment of water and increase the safety of its use.

However, when implementing electric discharge technologies, it is necessary to take into account all technical, sanitary and economic aspects in order to ensure optimal operation of the system and ensure consumer safety.

Proper purification and disinfection of water in district heating systems with open water intake is important in accordance with sanitary standards, in accordance with SanPiN 2.1.4.2496-09. According to these standards, the water quality in such systems must match the quality of drinking water in order to ensure safety for the health of consumers.

**Fig. 4 – Scheme for disinfection and purification of mains water:
1 – mixer; 2 – pump; 3 – bubbling adsorber; 4 – collection of purified water; 5 – ozonation plant; 6 – apparatus for purifying hot water**

To ensure the required level of water quality in district heating systems, it may be necessary to develop modern methods of water purification and disinfection. This may include the use of ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, ultraviolet irradiation, chlorination and other technologies.

Modern methods of water purification and disinfection in district heating systems make it possible not only to ensure compliance with sanitary standards, but also to increase the efficiency of the system, extend the service life of equipment and improve the quality of customer service.

It is important to carry out regular monitoring of water quality and the technical condition of equipment, as well as to comply with all sanitary norms and rules for the operation of district heating systems to ensure the safety and comfort of consumers [1-

7].

Diaphragm discharge (DER) is indeed an effective way to purify water from pathogenic microorganisms. During the operation of this technology, various physico-chemical processes occur in the diaphragm channel, such as cavitation, the formation of hydrogen peroxide, and the diffusion of metal ions from the surface of the electrodes. These processes create conditions favorable for water treatment and the destruction of pathogenic microorganisms.

In the process of diaphragm discharge, water decomposes into oxygen and hydrogen, which contributes to the formation of hydrogen peroxide. Hydrogen peroxide has strong disinfecting properties and is capable of destroying bacteria, viruses and other pathogenic microorganisms in water.

In addition, other active substances such as ozone, inorganic and organic radicals are formed during the diaphragm discharge process, which also contribute to improving water quality and disinfection.

Thus, the use of a diaphragm discharge to purify water from pathogenic microorganisms is an effective and innovative approach. The treated water can be used as a solution for disinfection of other surfaces and equipment, which increases the efficiency of the entire process of purification and disinfection of water in district heating systems.

This is a really interesting observation that shows the potential of diaphragm discharge (DER) in water disinfection. As I have already mentioned (a), the processes occurring in the diaphragm channel during the operation of the DARE create active substances such as hydrogen peroxide, ozone, radicals and others capable of destroying pathogenic microorganisms in water.

If the treated water containing these active substances is added to the infected stream in the right ratio, then it can really disinfect the entire stream. Hydrogen peroxide, for example, has powerful disinfecting properties and can destroy bacteria, viruses and other pathogens in water when properly dosed.

These are the results that could open up new prospects for the application of water disinfection methods using DER in district heating systems. However, for the widespread application of this approach, additional research and confirmation of experimental results are needed.

Nevertheless, such results complement our knowledge of the effectiveness of various water disinfection technologies and may contribute to the development of more efficient and safe methods of water purification and disinfection in district heating systems[3-11].

According to SNiP [10], the temperature for centralized hot water supply systems connected to open heat supply systems should be 60-75 0C.

Thus, the results of research at the DER installation are very interesting and have important practical significance for water disinfection and improving the efficiency of the system.

The dependence of the bactericidal activity of the plant on the water temperature indicates the importance of monitoring and regulating the temperature regime during water treatment. An increase in the temperature of the source water can increase the disinfection capacity of the system, which can be used to improve the purification process from pathogenic microorganisms.

In addition, the possibility of heating the mains water using this system is an additional practical advantage, since it allows you to reduce the flow rate from the supply pipeline and increase the efficiency of the entire system. Thus, the DARE system not only disinfects water, but also helps to optimize the processes of water supply and treatment.

Conclusion:

Modern methods of modernizing existing heat supply systems play an important role in improving their efficiency, safety and environmental sustainability. Despite the many problems that heat supply systems face, there are a number of innovative approaches to their modernization:

1. Installation of a smart control and monitoring system: The use of modern technologies (Internet of Things) and artificial intelligence allows you to create control systems that can optimize heat consumption, forecast demand and respond promptly to changes in load.

2. The use of highly efficient heat supply sources: The introduction of modern heat pumps, high-efficiency boilers, geothermal systems or solar collectors allows you to increase the energy efficiency of the system and reduce maintenance costs.

3. Development of combined heat supply systems: The use of modern technologies to combine various energy sources, such as gas, electricity, renewable sources, allows you to create more flexible and efficient systems that can adapt to changing needs.

4. Introduction of thermal insulation and insulation systems: Effective insulation of pipelines, buildings and equipment helps to reduce heat loss and increase the efficiency of the heat supply system.

5. Optimization of heat supply networks: The introduction of new technologies for monitoring and managing heat supply networks, as well as the reconstruction of outdated networks, reduces losses and improves the operation of the system as a whole.

Thus, the modernization of existing heat supply systems using modern technologies and innovative approaches can significantly increase their efficiency, reliability and environmental sustainability, which in turn will reduce maintenance

costs and make heat supply more economical and environmentally friendly.

THE LIST OF SOURCES USED.

1. Batukhtin, A.G. Methods of increasing efficiency and increasing the available capacity of district heating systems [text] / A.G. Batukhtin // Scientific problems of transport in Siberia and the Far East.– 2010. No. 1 p.– 189-192.
2. Khujaev P.S. Energy saving and increasing the energy efficiency of buildings by ensuring the effective operation of water supply and heat and gas supply systems// Khujaev P.S., Kholmuratov T.R., Bokiev B.R., Maramov M.B., Murodov P.H.// VESTNIK. Tajik National University. Series of geological and technical sciences 2023. No.1 ISSN 2664-1534 – pp.27-35.
3. Efimov, N.N. Prospects for the use of heat pumps in the energy supply of industrial and municipal enterprises [text] / N.N. Efimov, P.A. Malyshev // Thermal power engineering.- 2009. No.11. – pp. 30-33
4. Khujaev P.S. The use of solar energy in heating and hot water supply systems as an element of ecological housing, integration in the construction of individual housing.// Khujaev P.S., Pochchoev M.M.// Bulletin of the Tajik Technical University. Polytechnic Bulletin. Engineering Research series. No.1 (53) – 2021 C-155-159 Dushanbe 2021.
5. Petin, V.V. Modern technologies of using electric energy in district heating systems [text] / V.V. Petin, A.G. Batukhtin, A.V. Kalugin, P.G. Safronov//Scientific and Technical bulletin of St. Petersburg State Technical University– Spb.– 2010. No. 4.– pp. 32-38.
6. Khujaev P.S. On the duration of the heating period (article)// Sulaimonov A.A. Pochchoev M.M.// Bulletin of the Tajik National University. –Dushanbe, 2014. -№1/1(126). – Pp.86-99
7. Building codes and regulations. SNiP 2.04.01–85. Internal pipeline and sewerage of buildings. Moscow: Gosstroy of Russia. 1998
8. Khujaev P.S. Features of improving the operation of the ventilation system in underground communication structures// Saidgufonov B.P., Kholmuratov T.R., Abduganiev A. , Yakubov A.O., Maramov M // BIO Web of Conferences Volume 84 (2024) International Scientific and Practical Conference “Development and Modern Problems of Aquaculture” (AQUACULTURE 2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20248405039>.
9. Khujaev P.S. Improving the energy efficiency of low-power solid fuel hot water boilers. // E3S Web of Conf. Volume 452, 2023 XV International Online Conference “Improving Farming Productivity and Agroecology – Ecosystem Restoration” (IPFA 2023) Published online: 30 November 2023 DOI: <https://www.e3sconferences.org/articles/e3sconf/abs/2023/89/contents/contents.html>
10. SNiP 3.05.03-85 "Thermal networks" is no longer valid SNiP III-30-74 "Water supply, sewerage and heat supply.
11. SNiP III-G.6-62 Heat supply.
12. SNiP 41-02-2003 Thermal networks